

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Breeding method

Genetic studies of aroma in the elite cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) aromatic japonica line Shangbai A

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Medium-maturing Shangbai A possesses the male sterile cytoplasm of cultivar Chinsurah Boro II.

To study aroma inheritance, we crossed CMS line Shangbai A and its maintainer, Shangbai B, in 1989 with three nonaromatic restorer lines to obtain four crosses. In 1990, we backcrossed three of the F_1 with the CMS line used as maternal parent.

P_1, P_2, F_1, F_2 , and BC_1 progeny from the four crosses were sown in May 1991. Aroma from single plants was evaluated after 45 d. Leaf blades (2 g/plant) from each progeny were soaked in 10 ml of 1.7% KOH solution for 10 min at 25-30 °C. Panelists classified the samples as aromatic or nonaromatic by smelling the contents of the test tubes.

Expressions of aroma in leaf blade and grain were similar in Shangbai A and Shangbai B (Table 1). This implied that classifying aromatic/nonaromatic grains on the basis of leaf samples would be reliable.

F_1 plants from all the crosses were nonaromatic, indicating that aroma in Shangbai A (Shangbai B) was recessive (Table 2). Segregating ratios of nonaromatic to aromatic plants in BC_1 and F_2 were 1:1 and 3:1, respectively.

F_2 segregation behavior of Shangbai A/Zhi 7 and Shangbai B/Zhi 7 was identical. This indicates that the cytoplasm from Chinsurah Boro II did not affect expression of aroma in Shangbai A. Results showed that a recessive nuclear gene controls aroma in Shangbai A. □

Table 1. Percent accuracy for aromatic identification of 2-g leaf blade and grain samples and individual grain in Shangbai A and Shangbai B.

	Shangbai A		Shangbai B	
	Samples (no.)	Accuracy (%)	Samples (no.)	Accuracy (%)
2-g leaf blade ^a	30	100	19	100
2-g grain ^a	49	95.5	57	97.3
Individual grain ^b	83	84.4	73	90.4

^aTwo-gram samples were evaluated for aroma in 10 ml 1.7% KOH. ^bIndividual grains were evaluated in 5 ml 1.7% KOH.

Table 2. Behavior of parents (CMS, maintainers, and restorers), F_1 , BC_1 , and F_2 with regard to aroma.

Designation	Plants (no.)			Ratio of nonaromatic to aromatic		χ^2	P
	Tested	Nonaromatic	Aromatic	Actual	Expected		
Parent							
Shangbai A	30	0	30	0:1	0:1		
Shangbai B	19	0	19	0:1	0:1		
Zhi 7	21	21	0	1:0	1:0		
90-11	20	20	0	1:0	1:0		
4144	22	22	0	1:0	1:0		
F_1							
Shangbai A/Zhi 7	21	21	0	1:0	1:0		
Shangbai A/90-11	25	25	0	1:0	1:0		
Shangbai A/4144	23	23	0	1:0	1:0		
Shangbai B/Zhi 7	31	31	0	1:0	1:0		
BC_1							
Shangbai A/Shangbai A/Zhi 7	92	47	45	1:1.04	1:1	0.044	0.75-0.90
Shangbai A/Shangbai A/90-11	84	43	41	1:1.05	1:1	0.047	0.75-0.90
Shangbai A/Shangbai A/4144	101	49	52	0.94:1	1:1	0.089	0.75-0.90
Total	277	139	138	1.01:1	1:1	0.003	>0.90
F_2							
Shangbai A/Zhi 7	123	94	29	3.24:1	3:1	0.13	0.50-0.75
Shangbai A/90-11	160	115	45	2.55:1	3:1	0.77	0.25-0.50
Shangbai A/4144	158	119	39	3.05:1	3:1	0.01	>0.90
Shangbai B/Zhi 7	141	106	35	3.02:1	3:1	0.02	>0.90
Total	582	434	148	2.93:1	3:1	0.057	0.75-0.90

Effect of paper bags used to cover hand-crossed panicles on seed set and vigor

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White-colored glassine bags are usually used in hand-crossing rice panicles. We compared the effect of six types of paper bags on seed set and vigor of F_1 seeds in the MORIF greenhouse from Dec 1990 to Mar 1991 (see table).

The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized design with four

replications. IR48 was the female parent and IR42 the male. A vacuum emasculator was used. Hybrid seeds were harvested (100 from each replication) and sown.

Panicles covered with brown bread paper after pollination produced heavier seeds than panicles covered with white glassine bags (see table). One hundred seeds weighed 2.24 g for the brown bread paper, significantly more than the 1.5 g for the white glassine bag. Higher seed germination and seedling growth accompanied greater seed size. Bag type did not influence seed set percentage.

We determined the transmittance value of different bags with a DV-7